

Review

Nerve cells derived eosinophils chemoattractant and pathogenesis of eosinophilic esophagitis

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Esophageal eosinophilia is commonly observed in diverse medical problems including drug reactions, eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). (1-9) Characteristic endoscopic features observed in EoE patients include furrows, the formation of fine concentric mucosal rings (corrugated esophagus), extensive tissue remodeling, esophageal strictures and peristaltic dysfunction. (10-18) Several of these esophageal functional abnormalities are also observed in GERD patients. (12, 19, 20) EoE and GERD are closely related esophageal disorders and are differentiated by proton-pump inhibitor-responsiveness per esophageal eosinophilia guidelines(21) EoE is a global health issue and a mini-epidemic has been noted over the last two decades in both developed and non-developed countries. (10, 18, 22-29) The etiology of EoE is yet not entirely understood; but evidence indicates that food allergen induced inflammatory cells have an important role in the disease pathogenesis in children. (30-32) Allergen-induced IL-5 and IL-13 expression are implicated in the pathogenesis of EoE; but clinical trails employing anti-IL-5 and anti-IL-13 neutralization therapy have not yet achieved the desired goals of restricting esophageal eosinophila and basal cell hyperplasia. ^{13,53,65,6}In contrast, another

approach using CRTH2 antagonist in adults with EoE showed some promising benefits; (33, 34) but not been explored for the pathophysiological functional abnormalities in EoE. In recent years, major advances have also been made in understanding genetic associations in EoE patients. (35-37) However, yet the mechanism of esophageal fibrosis associated functional abnormalities such as dysphagia, and motility dysfunction and the effects of therapeutic interventions remains unclear for human EoE. Eotaxins is a well-established chemoattractant for eosinophils(35-37) and eotaxin-3 is highly induced in EoE patients. (38) However, the muscle cells are not the source of eotaxins; therefore it is critical to understand the other factors influence eosinophil and mast cell accumulation and activation in the esophageal mucosa. We have earlier provided the evidence that eosinophil and mast cells accumulate and release their mediators in the muscular mucosa in EoE, (38) and that this in turn promotes esophageal functional abnormalities. (39) Most recently, we showed that eosinophils accumulate in the muscular mucosa of the mouse and human esophagus. However, the mechanisms that drive eosinophil and mast cell accumulation and activation in and beyond the esophageal epithelial mucosa that is

likely promote pathophysiological functional abnormalities in EoE is not well understood. Several studies have demonstrated the potential role of nerve cells derived neuropeptides in eosinophil recruitment, (40, 41) and mast cell activation and degranulation. (42) Therefore, neuroimmune interactions may be possible for the eosinophil and mast cell accumulation and degranulation in EoE or GERD. Earlier, we also reported that eosinophil accumulate nearby induced vasoactive intestinal peptide (VIP) expressing nerve cells along with the VIP specific receptors on eosinophils and mast cells in the biopsies of human EoE. VIP is secreted by nerve cells and earlier implicated in the pathogenesis of eosinophil associated allergic diseases. (43-45) VIP binds to its specific receptors such as vasoactive intestinal peptide receptor 1 (VPAC-1), VPAC-2 and chemoattractant receptor-homologous molecule CRTH2. (40, 41) These findings provide an understanding and rationale for the reported benefits of the CRTH2 antagonist in adult EoE patients. (33, 34) Furthermore, several other molecules such as TSLP, TGF β and VCAM-1 are implicated in the pathogenesis of EoE and are induced by VIP in other allergic or autoimmune diseases. (46-48). IgE and residential mast cells interaction releases histamine that activate nerve cells to induce VIP most probably in human EoE. VIP receptor CRTH2 is shown to restrict eosinophils and mast cells motility in experimental and human EoE. Even though, CRTH2 is also expressed on CD4 T cells, which is the source of eosinophil active IL-5 and IL-13; therefore, the possibility that these cells may also respond to VIP. Notably, these cytokines have no chemotactic activity for eosinophils, but they may help in the survival and proliferation of eosinophil that accumulates in response to VIP. Taken together, these reports highlight

the significance of nerve cells derived chemoattractants in the pathogenesis of EoE functional abnormalities. Therefore, attention should be give to understand the role of neuroimmune axis in promoting EoE pathogenesis including esophageal functional abnormalities, such esophageal motility dysfunction.

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